

Quality of Silage made from Fodder crops and its mixture

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Manuscript details:

Received: 09.04.2026
Accepted: 18.05.2026
Published: 30.05.2026

Cite this article as:

Smita Basole (2026) Quality of Silage made from Fodder crops and its mixture, *Int. J. of Life Sciences*, 14 (1A): 227-230. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20685447>

Available online on <http://www.ijlsci.in>
ISSN: 2320-964X (Online)
ISSN: 2320-7817 (Print)

ABSTRACT

Several species were found suitable for higher fodder production. Properly selected green fodder is the most natural food for animals. In India owing to climatic conditions and other limitations it is difficult to raise organised pasture. Green fodder has fairly high nutritive value with good number of digestible proteins. Converting green fodder in silage, preserve the food value. Investigation reported in this paper was under taken mainly to study the effect of mixing two different crops for the preparation of silage and study the nutritive quality of resultant silage.

Keywords: fodder, silage, crop mixture, raring animals, Anaerobic Fermentation

INTRODUCTION

In Indian agricultural practices the farmers need animals to conduct different agriculture works and to obtained various animal products. An impressive advance has been made in the Indian agriculture since independence in achieving self-sufficiency in food grain production. However, the production of milk and other animal products is not satisfactory, in spite of having judge livestock population. One of the main reasons for low productivity of livestock is under nutrition and malnutrition there is vast gap between demand and supply of all kind of food and feed material. It has been realised long back fodder resources of India are inadequate (Relwani, 1979). The livestock derived its feed mainly from cultivated fodder crops apart from grassland crop residue fodder trees etc.

The ration of animal mainly divided into two parts one for maintenance and other for production purpose. Whatever diet supplied to animal over and above its maintenance requirement is available for production such as growth production of cough production of milk and output of work (Sen, 1978) out of this milk is mostly most widely used product of livestock as it is rich in proteins, fats, lactose, vitamins, calcium and phosphorus. It is therefore obvious that the animal must be provided with sufficient quantities of all nutrients through feed in addition to maintenance requirement. To fulfil the demand of fodder in bulk great importance is being paid on the evolvment high yielding, short duration

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and nutritive varieties of fodder crops. But it has been observed that very little area of land is used for fodder production in India leads to scarcity of animal feed. Adequate supply of green fodder is possible during rainy season or with well irrigated farms condition in order to supply fodder during scarcity or in summer season conservation of surplus fodder in the form of hay is very common practice in India (Patel et al 1968) observe considerable loss of beta carotene during hay making mainly due to slow and spontaneous oxidation of these pigments (Seshan and Sen 1942).

Another method of conserving green fodder is the preparation of silage. Silage is a product formed when any green plant material is fermented in absence of air the ensiled material contains enough sugars and stored anaerobically, lactic acid bacteria in the material multiply rapidly and formed lactic acid. This lactic acid preserves the silage (Allen et al 1937). The preservation of herbage depends on rapid acidification of mass by lactic acid producing bacteria which reduces pH value range between 3.8 TO 4.2. During ensiling extensive protein breakdown takes place in the very early stages of ensiling due to the activity of plant proteases (Kamble, 1956). Deficiency of fermentable carbohydrate in the material slow down. The development of lactobacilli and inadequate degree of acidity leads to Clostridial or secondary fermentation such silages generally results in storage loss, poor chemical quality, offensive odour and low dry matter in take by ruminant. Therefore, silage making is to be conducted very carefully and with proper crops or crop mixture.

Experiment:

Several fodder crops have been recommended for cultivation and ensuing feeding to cattle these includes no leguminous and leguminous crops. While cultivating this crop proper agronomic practice have to be followed for maximum fodder production. All field trials were conducted at Dr Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University Botanical Garden, the piece of land was prepared by ploughing and cross ploughing. The land is divided into plots each bearing 16.48 m². The sowing was done by hand in rows 30.5 CM apart. All field trials were conducted in randomised block design (RBD) with three replicates. The crops were harvested for green fodder with still cutter early in the morning and harvesting was done generally at pre-flowering stage. Fresh green fodder obtained was brought into the laboratory immediately after

harvesting the crop material was chopped into 3-4 CM pieces and some material was used for drying in an electric oven at 95^o C which determine dry matter contain after 48 hours. The crops were chopped in small pieces and used for preparation of silage

PREPARATION OF SILAGE

The chopped plant material was placed in plastic container (16.5 x 9 CM) and press to make it compact and exclude air. The container was covered with lid, mouth of container was capped and seal with wax. This made the container air tight to maintain anaerobic condition for ensiled plant material. The container or laboratory silo were kept at room temperature in dark, until used. The laboratory silos were kept at room temperature for 30 days. After 30 days the boxes were open and physical characteristics that is colour texture order where examine of resulted silage samples. Sample of fresh silage was taken for the determination of pH, buffering capacity, titra table acidity and others sample was dried in the electric oven till constant weight obtained. The dried sample where ground to a fine powder and used for subsequent analysis

ANALYSIS

40 grams of fresh silage sample was mixed with 40 ml of distil water place on cotton cloth priest and the juice was collected in the beaker the pH was measure using glass electrol to determine titra table acidity 5 grams of fresh silage was macerated with 75 ml distilled water boiled for few minutes filtered through cotton cloth diluted up to 100 ml titrated against 0.1 N NaOH solution using phenolphthalein indicator. Total volatile fatty acids (TVFA) where estimated by steam distillation method describe by Choudhary (1970), buffering capacity was determined following Playne and McDonald (1966) lactic acid was estimated using method of Barker and Summerson (1941) as described by Oser 1979.

1 gram of dried sample was boiled in water filtered through whatmann filter paper and filtrate was used for measurement of water-soluble reducing sugar (WSRS) in terms of glucose using Folin-Wu tubes Oser (1979). The nitrogen content was determined by using micro-jeldahl method with sulphuric acid in presence of catalyst and titration of ammonia liberated during distillation (Bailey 1967). The value of crude protein was expressed as n into 6.25 (Oser, 1970) methods were followed for estimation of crude fat, ash, acid

soluble ash, nitrogen free extract, total carbohydrates and calcium. Hennburg acid alkali gravimetric method describe by Lees 1968 was followed for estimation of crude fibre. The content of phosphorus was estimated following Fisk and Subbarao (1925) describe by Oser

(1979). All samples were analysed in duplicate and wherever necessary that data was subjected to statistical analysis following Panse and Sukhatme 1978.

Table 1: Chemical compositions of silages

Crop	% Moisture	Titrateable Acidity m-equiv/ 100g DM	Buffering Capacity m-equiv/ 100g DM	pH	Total Volatile Fatty Acid (TVFA) mM / 100g	Water Soluble Reducing Sugars (% of DM)
Bajra	79.5	79.5	17.0	4.35	9.6	2.1
Sorghum	76.0	45.2	38.7	3.65	8.6	2.05
Cowpea	80.0	87.5	33.5	5.74	8.4	1.05
Dolichos	74.5	61.6	58.2	4.64	8.6	0.95
Bajra+ Cowpea	79.4	71.6	35.0	5.54	7.0	0.85
Sorghum + Dolichos	80.0	58.0	48.9	4.38	7.4	1.04
Cowpea + Dolichos	80.5	76.9	61.5	5.84	2.6	1.15

Crop	% Dry Matter (DM)	% Of Dry Matter (DM)								
		Crude Protein	Crude Fibre	Crude Fat	Ash	ASA	NFE	TC	Ca	Pi
Bajra	20.5	15.0	34.3	4.3	16.2	12.9	30.2	64.5	0.33	0.22
Sorghum	22.5	17.8	30.5	3.9	15.7	11.3	32.1	62.6	0.89	0.22
Cowpea	20.0	20.7	25.4	1.8	16.8	6.8	35.3	60.8	1.00	0.43
Dolichos	25.5	20.9	26.4	2.9	20.3	10.3	29.5	55.9	1.35	0.73
Bajra+ Cowpea	20.6	18.7	32.3	4.7	18.3	12.1	26.0	58.3	0.74	0.19
Sorghum + Dolichos	20.0	20.5	31.2	2.8	14.7	9.8	30.8	62.0	1.79	0.40
Cowpea + Dolichos	19.5	19.4	32.3	1.8	19.7	13.1	27.7	59.4	1.42	0.37

All silage samples were good in condition without any foul smell and microbial growth. The silages made from either Bajra, *Sorghum*, *Cowpea* or *Dolichos* solely or mixture of Bajra and *Cowpea*, *Sorghum* and *Dolichos* and *Cowpea* and *Dolichos*. The moisture content in resulted silages 70.4 to 80.5. A significance variation was observed in the values for titrateable acidity among the silages due to nature of ensiled material. The buffering capacity (BC) varied widely however, the variation is not significant. Silage made from bajra had lower BC, may be due to low protein content in it. (Reddy and Mungikar 1987). In all silage samples pH is more than 4.35 except in Sorghum. It was as high as 5.84 in Cowpea + Dolichos silage. Macdonald and Henderson (1962) suggested that a good silage has pH within the rage of 3.8 to 4.2. In view of this all-silage samples were not up to the mark. The dry matter content is also high in Dolichos (25.5 %) than that

made from mixture of Dolichos +Cowpea (19.5%). Protein content is varied between 15.0 to 20.9 indicate suitability of material in animal nutrition.

All silage sample contained other nutrient except calcium in considerable quantity fore animal feeding. All silages samples particularly made from mixture of legume and non-legume crops content enough nutrient for maintenance and production of farm animals.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable.

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